

Degree and the Effect of Order in the Family on Violence against Women (VAW)

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Abstract—The purpose of this study attempts to emphasize the factors relating to intra-family relationships (order point of view) on violence against the women, For this purpose a survey technique on the sample size amounted 100 women of married of city of Ilam in country of Iran were considered. For measurement of violence against the women , the CTS scaled has been used .violence against the women be measured in four dimension (emotional violence, psycho violence, physical violence, neglect violence). highest violence was related to emotional violence and after are as follow respectively : physical violence and neglect violence. The results showed that women have experienced the violence more than once during the last year, degree of order in family is high. Explanation result indicated that the order variables in family including collective thinking, empathy and communal co-circumstance have significant effects on violence against the women. Via multiple regression analysis variables of empathy, religious tenet and education of husband had significant effect on violence against women. In other words relationships among family effect on violence in family.

Keywords—violence, domestic violence, violence against women, family.

I.INTRODUCTION

VIOLENCE makes life rough and imposition, also causes psychological and physical injuries which will never be improved. Women and children are more in the center of attack. Children are affected by domestic violence in a variety of ways. Domestic violence in the household is often accompanied by other major developmental risk factors for children such as poverty, female-headed Household and low education level of primary care giver [1].Adult domestic violence is also associated with child abuse [2]. There is evidence that children who are victims of or Witnesses to domestic violence have more emotional and social problems than children not exposed to such violence [3]. It has also been found that developmental impairments and psychological

problems may affect these children throughout adolescence and into adulthood [4]. Child exposure to adult domestic violence is associated with significantly greater behavioral, emotional, and cognitive functioning problems among children, as well as adjustment difficulties that continue into young adulthood [5].

A considerable amount of child additionally disposes on physical violence at the home directly, effect of violence indirectly through enforcement of violence of father on Mother, children will be injured mentally and physically. A 1996 survey by the Australian Bureau of Statistics found that 23% of women who have been married or in a de facto relationship have experienced violence a partner [6].Sixty eight percent of women who had experienced violence in a previous relationship stated that at some time during the relationship they had children in their care [6]. Forty six percent of these women said that these children had witnessed the violence. Straus [7] Thompson, Saltzman, and Johnson [8] report that 33.2% of 962 Children and Youth Canadian abused women and 40.2% of US battered women responding in national surveys stated that their children had witnessed domestic violence events.

More recent meta-analyses by Kitzmann, Gaylord, Holt, and Kenny [9] and Wolfe, Crooks, Lee, McIntyre-Smith, and Jaffe [10] have shown children exposed to domestic violence to exhibit significantly worse problems than children not so exposed 963 It is estimated that between 20 and 30% of women and 7.5% of men have been physically and/or sexually abused by an intimate partner at so me point in their lives [11]. Fifty percent of all female homicides are the result of intimate partner violence [12].Chronic but often non-specific problems are often reported by the adult victim. They include headaches, sleep disorders, GI discomfort and bowel problems, depression, fatigue, anxiety and post traumatic stress disorder [13]. Research examining the effects of domestic violence on young children revealed that, according to mother's reports, half of the children witnessed at least 60% of the violence [14]. These findings indicate a major social problem which has long term negative effects on children. These effects include anxiety, depression, aggressive behavior, decreased self-esteem, disobedience, emotional distress and carrying out abuse in the future [15].

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This paper tries to cover the violence against women (VAW) in the Family.

Framework:

For domestic violence are many definitions. Tailor and Garbarino pay attention to nature of violence, Some of other scholar have mentioned some factors related to violence such as dystrophy, parents disability in satisfying children with enough food, sanitary problems, dirty places for living, preventing children from school, punishing and... [16]. Behaviors often attributed to domestic violence exposure may also derive from the child's concurrent victimization at the hands of his or her parent or caregiver [5]. The wide range of behaviors and consequences associated with exposure to domestic violence found in these reviews indicate that the relationship between exposure and possible impacts is complex [17]. There are many models for explanation of domestic violence e.g Wolf have posed transitional model for intensity of conflict between parents and children, in this model stress is a factor which intensifies the probability conflicts among family. Parents disability on facing the problems in their lives cause VAC. Tonti man and his colleagues have posed cognitive-behavioral model. Mack fal have posed social information processing model [18] Life cycle model by Reder and Duncan ,this model pays attention to the international theories which in turn emphasis on VAC[19]. For defining of domestic violence served models have been used, including theories which have regarded the family inter relations. To achieve this we have used the Chalabi model which is base on Parsons theory.

Chalabi explains that "interactions and individuals" are two main factors within order formation in families and combination of these two brings order, at micro-level. in the A.G.I.L Parsons framework tells with the formation of "us" we can speak of a kind of micro social order. This social order, instantaneously, involves "individuals", "interactions", and "us". the "us" which is based on "individuals" and "interactions". To preserve "orders" and "interaction patterns", micro social order confront four problems[19]. including: 1- collective thinking (L), 2- company (G) 3- empathy (I), and 4-communal circumstance(A) [20].

II. METHOD

This research is survey and information have been collected by questioner, population is the city of Ilam in Iran , samples are 100 women of married of city of Ilam in country of Iran were considered in 2008 , selected by sample of systematic random. Reliability and validity of variables have been considered, by scale of Alpha and Factor analysis.

Measurement:

A. Order in Family (Independent Variables)

For measuring order in family used been below variables:

1. Collective thinking 2. Company 3. Empathy 4. communal circumstance. Each independent variables by codes : never=0, very little = 1, little= 2, moderate = 3 , much = 4 , very much = 5 , ever = 6, e.g. questions raised to this way:" To which extent there has been consult within your family"?

Never very little little moderate much
very much

operational independent variables are available at Table I.

Questioner of order in family:

1. To which extent there has been consult on children nurture within you husband?
2. To which extent there has been consult on families meeting within your husband?
3. To which extent there has been consult on buying house wares within your husband?
4. How much loves each other?
5. How much does your love to your husband?
6. To which extent you ignore your interests and claims in the favor of other family members?
7. To which extent your husband ignore interests and claims in the favor of other family members?
8. To which extent do your husband ignore traveling your in the favor of other family members?
9. How much are you patient?
10. How much is your husband patient?
11. How much will you be worried if your husband faces a problem?

B. Domestic Violence (Dependent Variables)

One of the most common methods of measuring child exposure, as stated earlier, is to adapt the adult Conflict Tactics Scales [21],[22] for use with children. Kolbo [23] utilized the same seven-point scale as the original CTS, with responses ranging from "Never" to "Over 20 Times"

VAC will be category to 3 levels: 1- emotional abuse 2- physical abuse 3- neglect.

For measuring VAC used been CTS scale: Each independent variables by codes : 0=never, 1 = 1-2 times ,2 = 3-5 times,3 = 6-10 times, 4 = 11-20 times,5 =over 20 times. e.g. questions raised to this way:" How many times has it happened that your father has prevented you from speaking during the last year "?

Never 1-2 times 3-5 times 6-10 times 11-20 times Over 20 times

Operational dependent variables (VAW) are available at Table II.

III. RESULT

Questioner of violence against the children:

1. How many times has it happened that your husband has prevented you of speaking during the last year?
2. How many times has it happened that your husband has broken self esteem your during last year?
3. How many times has it happened that your husband has threaded you during last year?
4. How many times has it happened that your husband shouted you during last year?
5. How many times has it happened that your husband forced you do sth during last year?
6. How many times has it happened that your husband has been injustice during last year?
7. How many times has it happened that your husband neglected your sickness during last year?
8. How many times has it happened that your husband neglected your being late you during last year?
9. How many times has it happened that your husband forced you to leave home during last year?
10. How many times has it happened that your husband pushed you during last year?
11. How many times has it happened that your husband beat you during last year?
12. How many times has it happened that your husband cussed you during last year?
13. How many times has it happened that your husband reproaching for food during last year?
14. How many times has it happened that your husband threaded you to divorce during last year?

Result of descriptive order in family:

Table I show descriptive statistic of order in family, in this table we see percent of variables: collective thinking, empathy, company, communal circumstance. The frequency of distribution of order in family shown in Table I. mean of variables among (0-5) have been scaled: code (0) never, code (1) very little, code (2) little, code (3) moderate, code (4) much, code (5) very much. collective thinking: highest mean for collective thinking is variable of consult on buying house wares (mean= 3.79) the other variables are: consult on families meeting (mean =3.61), consult on children nurture, (mean=3.47). empathy: highest mean for empathy is variable loves each other (mean=3.97), the other variables are: love to spouse (mean=3.96). Company: Highest mean for company is variable ignoring interests by woman (mean=3.62) and after is ignoring interests by man (mean=3.59). Communal circumstance: Highest mean for communal circumstance is variable of wife worry if husband faces a problem (mean = 4.26), the other variables are: patient of husband (mean = 3.92), wife patient (mean =3.28). Concerning compute of variables of order in family, mean order in family is 3.69 among 0-5, this illustrate order in family is moderate (more than moderate), the most share of order in family is empathy (mean 3.97) in family and the others are: communal circumstance (mean 3.85), collective thinking (mean 3.62) and company (mean 3.45).

TABLE I
 DISTRIBUTION OF FREQUENCIES ORDER IN FAMILY

Very much	much	moderate	little	Very little	never	variable	index
28%	29%	24%	8%	8%	4%	Consult on children nurture	Collective thinking
24.2%	39.4%	21.2%	7.1%	5.1%	3%	Consult on families meeting	
33%	35%	19%	6%	5%	2%	Consult on buying house wares	
46%	27%	14%	5%	7%	1%	love to each other	empathy
49%	21%	16%	7%	6%	1%	Love to husband	
31%	25%	30%	6%	5%	3%	Ignore wife interest in the favor of other members	company
14%	31%	32%	12%	5%	6%	Ignore husband interest in the favor of other members	
37%	38%	10%	10%	5%	0	husband patient	communal circumstance
22%	29%	25%	15%	7%	2%	Wife patient	

44.2%	14.1%	9.5%	1.5%	2.5%	4%	Wife worry if husband faces a problem
62%	19%	10%	3%	4%	2%	Children worry if mother faces a problem

IV. RESULT DESCRIPTIVE OF VAW

Table II show the results of descriptive of VAW (dependence variable) mean and frequencies of variables among (0-6) have been scaled :code (0) never, code (1) one-two times , code (2) 3-5 times , code (3) 6-10 times, code (4) 11-20 times, code (5) more 20 times.

Emotional abuse: highest mean (among never- over 20 time) for Emotional abuse of husband is variable of shouting (mean =1.85), that 74.7% wives have experienced the violence at more than once during the last year, and other variables are: injustice (mean=1.15) that 45% wives have experienced the violence more than once during the last year , preventing from speak (mean=1.14) that 50% wives have experienced the violence more than once during the last year, Breaking of self esteem (mean=1.18) 53%wives have experienced the violence more than once during the last year, force to doing Sth (mean=1.07) that 50% wives have experienced the violence more than once during the last year , treating (mean =1.84) that 32% wives have experienced the violence more than once during the last year.

Neglect: highest mean for neglect is variable of neglect to sickness (mean =0.92) that 39% wives have experienced the violence at least once during the more than, and the others variables are: Neglect to being late (mean = 0.73) that 31% wives have experienced the violence more than once during the last year, forcing to leave home (mean = 0.53) that 26% wives have experienced the violence more than once during the last year, expelling o home (mean = 0.40) that 14% wives

have experienced the violence more than once during the last year.

Physical abuse: highest mean for Physical abuse is variable of pushing (mean =0.59) that 27 % children have experienced the violence more than once during the last year, and after as follows: beating (mean =0.48) that 11% children have experienced the violence more than once during the last year.

Psycho abuse: highest mean for psycho abuse is variable of reproaching for food (mean =1.44) that 63 % wives have experienced the violence more than once during the last year, and after as follows: cussing (mean =1) that 43% wives have experienced the violence more than once during the last year, treat to divorce (mean =0.89) that 33% wives have experienced the violence more than once during the last year.

Concerning compute of variables violence against the children, mean VAW in family among never (0) – over 20 times (6) is 1.1 that Illustrate wives have experienced the violence more than once during the last year, the most share of violence in family is emotional abuse (mean 1.18) and others :psycho abuse(mean 1.11), physical abuse(mean .70),neglect (mean .68) .

TABLE II
 DISTRIBUTION OF FREQUENCIES OF VAW

Over 20 times	11-20 times	6-10 times	3-5 times	1-2 times	never	variables	index
5%	4%	7%	18%	16%	50%	Preventing from speaking	husband's emotional abuse
7%	5%	7%	9%	25%	47%	Breaking of self esteem	
2%	7%	7%	7%	9%	68%	treating	
11.1%	9.1%	12%	15.2%	27.3%	25.3%	shouting	
8%	7%	4%	9%	17%	55%	Force to doing sth	
5.6%	2.5%	2.5%	9.1%	9.1%	62.1%	injustice	neglect
7%	1%	2%	7%	14%	69%	neglect to sickness	
7%	1%	2%	7%	14%	69%	Neglect to being late	
0	0	3%	1.5%	5%	84.4%	forcing to leave home	
2%	3%	4%	2%	15%	74%	Expelling of home	
4%	2%	3%	4%	14%	73%	pushing	husband's

4%	1%	1%	6%	9%	79%	beating	physical abuse
7%	4%	3%	11%	17%	57%	reproaching for food	husband's psycho abuse
7%	4%	3%	11%	17%	57%	cussing	
5%	5%	8%	5%	10%	67%	treat to divorce	

V. STATISTIC TESTS

By Pearson test correlation between independent variables and VAW show this result (Table IV): Concerning Table IV, effect of order in the family on VAW is significance (intensity = -0.742, SIG = 000), that illustrate the increase of collective thinking in family, decrease VAW and also dimension of order in the family are : effect of collective thinking on VAW is significance (intensity = -0.657, SIG = 000), that illustrate the increase of collective thinking in family, decrease VAW, effect of empathy on VAW is significance (intensity = -0.754, SIG = 000), that illustrate the

increase of empathy in family ,decrease VAW, effect of communal circumstance on VAW is significance (intensity = -0.487, SIG = 000), that illustrate the increase of communal circumstance in family, decrease VAW. effect of company on VAW is significance (intensity = -0.433, SIG = 000), that illustrate the increase of company in family decrease VAW .Which means the variables of collective thinking, empathy and communal circumstance will decrease the amount VAW, which in turn verifies the interaction effects families' violence against the children.

TABLE IV
 PEARSON TEST CORRELATION AMONG VAW N AND ORDER IN FAMILY AND ITS DEMENSIONS

	Order in the family	empathy	Collective thinking	company	communal Co-circumstance
VAW	-0.742**	-0.454**	-0.657**	-0.433**	-0.487**

**p < .01

also religious of spouse has negative effect on VAW (intensity = -.438, SIG = 000) , that illustrate the increase of religious in family ,decrease VAW.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper investigates the effects of order in family VAW in a survey method by CTS scale. For defining children VAW we have used theories which emphasis on factors of relations and interaction among family members. order in family with regard to the following variables has been operational as a whole. the rate of order family is moderate .with CTS scale VAW has been operational and its rate is 1.1 among 0-6, that wives have experienced more than once during the last year. Variables order in the family and its dimension include:

collective thinking empathy, communal circumstance are significant, this shows its important in realizing the effective factors on violence in family, in other words relationships among family effect on violence in family, then this research prove theories factors relating to intra-family relationships.

Among the peripheral variables , variable rate of religious is significant, that illustrate the increase of religious in family, decrease VAW. The other peripheral variables e.g income, education and profession related to family violence are not significant. All these show that VAW is more related to relational factors in inter of family.

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